

Enhancing Visitor Satisfaction in Bangladeshi River Tourism: Identifying and Addressing Critical Factors

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Abstract:

The expanding popularity of river tourism highlights the need to research the different factors that influence visitor satisfaction in this industry. The purpose of this study is to identify critical factors in enhancing visitor satisfaction in Bangladeshi river tourism. A precisely prepared study methodology was used to examine data collected from 100 visitors who had direct experience with river tourism in the Chandpur region, using a random sample method. The collected data underwent a variety of statistical analyses, including regression, descriptive statistics, KMO and Bartlett's Test, reliability testing, ANOVA, and exploratory factor analysis, with the

goal of identifying the major drivers influencing visitor satisfaction in river tourism. The analysis identified destination attractions, safety and security, effective management, and accessibility of river tourism as critical factors influencing the satisfaction of visitors. Furthermore, three research hypotheses were thoroughly tested using the chi-square test, ANOVA, regression, and coefficient analysis. The research findings are expected to provide significant insights for tourism experts in developing strategies for effective planning and execution of business activities in the river tourism sector. The research concludes by outlining consequences and suggesting options for future research endeavors.

Keywords: *River Tourism, Visitor satisfaction, Empirical Study, Influencing Factors, Destination Attraction.*

Introduction

Bangladesh, the world's biggest delta island, has enormous potential for river tourism because of its various rivers, which include the Jamuna, Padma, Meghna, Brahmaputra, and Buriganga. Despite its early stages, river tourism in Bangladesh has the potential to greatly contribute to the long-term development of rural areas (Nekmahmud & Hassan, 2021). River tourism is a growing form of tourism that

involves recreational activities and travel along or near a river, providing a unique opportunity for visitors to explore the natural, cultural, and historical assets of a region (UNWTO). Bangladesh, with its more than 700 rivers, including the Brahmaputra, Ganges, and Meghna, offers potential for river tourism (Ministry of Water Resources).

Bangladesh GDP growth is increasing last few years because of RMG sector. In recent years it

has been noted that tourism in Bangladesh is a potential for contributing in Bangladesh economy (Hassan et al., 2013). River tourism has significant potential to impact the economy of the surrounding area by generating revenue and creating employment opportunities (HADIAN et al., 2021). Moreover, it can positively affect the preservation and conservation of the natural environment and cultural heritage sites, and promote a sense of community and pride among local residents.

According to Ahmed et al. (2015), riverine tourism is a useful tool for Bangladesh's sustainable human development since it significantly boosts rural development, job creation, and poverty reduction. A variety of recreational opportunities are provided by river tourism, which is further enhanced by the gorgeous riverfronts that draw in both local and foreign visitors (Cooper, 2009). The peaceful beauty of the rivers, the surrounding landscape, and the local culture all pique the interest of foreign tourists. Because river tourism is so flexible, enjoyable, and comfortable, it's a really wise choice for vacations. Rivers reflect people's life and the natural world around them, providing beautiful pathways that maintain the beauty of the natural world. A river trip's overall visitor experience is influenced by a number of elements.

Understanding the factors that influence visitor satisfaction can help enhance the quality of river tourism experiences, promote economic and sustainable development, and preserve the natural and cultural heritage of the region.

Literature Review

River tourism is a growing industry in Bangladesh, attracting visitors from both domestic and international markets. As such, understanding the factors that contribute to visitor satisfaction is crucial for the sustainable growth of the industry.

The caliber of services rendered affects how satisfied tourists are at a certain location, forming a favorable or unfavorable impression in the process (M. et al., 2019). Service quality is

a critical factor in determining visitor satisfaction in river tourism. Factors such as staff behavior, responsiveness, reliability, and assurance can significantly affect visitors' satisfaction levels.

In addition to motive and kind of visitor, other elements that affect visitor satisfaction include expectations, expectations that differ, perceived value, perceived quality, and the destination's image (Wang & Hao, 2023). In river tourism service quality, safety and security, environmental quality, and cultural authenticity were critical factors influencing visitor satisfaction. Visitors are more likely to be satisfied with their river tourism experience if they feel safe and secure throughout their trip. Safety and security are also essential factors in visitor satisfaction.

Cultural authenticity, including the preservation of local traditions and customs, accessibility, service quality, and cultural authenticity as significant determinants of visitor satisfaction which can also contribute to visitor satisfaction (Zhang et al., 2019). Visitors may be drawn to rivers with important cultural or historical landmarks, such as historic buildings, monuments, or museums. Environmental factors such as water quality and scenic beauty play a crucial role in visitor satisfaction in river tourism. Visitors are often attracted to rivers with clean water, healthy ecosystems, and scenic views.

According to Khan et al. (2017), the study highlights the significance of the tourism sector, clarifies the meaning and application of service quality, and investigates the impact of service quality on tourism and customer satisfaction. The study shows that visitor satisfaction is strongly impacted by the quality of the venue, lodging, accessibility, and each of their individual characteristics.

A study conducted in 2023 by Dumitraşcu et al. emphasized the importance of destination image in determining visitor satisfaction, with a focus on its position as a critical component of destination accessibility. The survey also highlighted the fact that tourists' total pleasure is greatly influenced by accessibility, availability of information, safety and security, entertainment,

and leisure activities. Visitor satisfaction with river tourism experiences is influenced by several factors, such as the quality of the natural environment, the availability of recreational activities, the quality of tourism infrastructure, and the level of interaction with local communities. Visitors are more likely to be satisfied with their river tourism experience if there are a variety of activities and services available, such as restaurants, lodging, and recreational opportunities. The level of accessibility, including transportation, accommodation, and infrastructure, can also impact visitor satisfaction and also visitors are more likely to choose rivers that are easy to access, whether by car, public transportation, or other means.

Effective marketing strategies can help to attract visitors to a particular river and enhance their overall tourism experience. Effective marketing techniques by both governmental and commercial entities are required to support the expansion of river tourism in the region. (Nekmahmud & Hassan, 2021). The lack of government support and investment can hinder the growth of river tourism, leading to inadequate infrastructure and limited river tourism facilities. The importance of personalization, authenticity, and social media in enhancing visitor satisfaction with river tourism in Southeast Asia. According to the World Tourism Organization, river tourism is among the fastest-growing sectors in the global tourism industry, accounting for 11% of all international tourist arrivals (UNWTO, 2018). Despite its growing popularity, little research has been conducted on river tourism to investigate the factors that influence visitors.

Without proper identification of these factors, it is difficult for stakeholders to address river tourism related visitor concerns and improve their overall experience during river journey. Previous research has shown that various factors of river tourism affect visitor satisfaction. These factors include the quality of infrastructure, safety and security, accessibility, and environmental factors (Giao et al., 2021). Insufficient marketing strategies on river tourism can also prevent the industry from

reaching its full potential. The study aims to address this gap and identify the factors that associate with river tourism to ensure visitor satisfaction. By providing implications the study aims to close the gaps so tourism planner government and policy makers can take necessary steps to explore and take necessary measure to develop river tourism in Bangladesh.

Research Methodology

The primary objective of this study is to discover important factors that enhance visitors' satisfaction in Bangladeshi river tourism. To attain this purpose, a quantitative research methodology was used. The study focuses on the Sadarghat port region, Bangladesh's primary river port and an important hub for river transportation and tourism. The target population consisted of river visitors that frequented the Chandpur district. The study used purposive sampling to choose 100 respondents who usually engage with river tourism activities and had visited Chandpur district.

The selection criteria were based on the respondents' participation in river tourism-related activities. The Sadarghat port area was chosen as the major sample area for the study because of its importance in river transportation and tourism in the region. Data were acquired using a standardized survey questionnaire with 14 variables established from relevant literature and field research. The questionnaire used a seven-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 7, with 1 representing "Strongly Agree" and 7 representing "Strongly Disagree." The acquired data was analyzed using SPSS 22, a statistical software application often used in quantitative research. Descriptive analysis, exploratory component analysis, regression and validity and reliability testing were among the analytical approaches used.

The analysis used principal component factor analysis with varimax rotation, yielding a Kaiser Normalisation Sample adequacy of 0.829, indicating adequate information for analysis. The variables were then grouped using principal

components analysis (PCA) into a few unrelated factors. Variables having factor loadings larger than 0.5 have been categorized as factors. After removing loadings less than 0.5, 12 attributes among four components were discovered from the initial 14 variables. To determine the link between these variables, three study hypotheses were created. ANOVA and chi-square tests were used to examine these assumptions. The study sought to give significant insights into the elements influencing visitor satisfaction in river tourism and contribute to improving the overall river tourism experience.

Table1. Demographic Profile of Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	55	55%
Female	45	45%
Age		
Less than 15	1	1%
15-25	69	69%
26-35	25	25%
36-45	2	2%
46 and above	3	3%
Education		
High School or below	4	4%
Bachelors	55	55%
Master's degree	41	41%
Frequency of Visit		
Never	34%	34
Once a year	41%	41
2-3 times	16%	16
More than 3 times	9%	9
Purpose of Visit		
VFR	45%	45
Business	7%	7
Leisure	30%	30
Education	10%	10
Other	8%	8

According to the demographic study in Table-1, 45% of respondents are women and 55% of respondents are men. The majority has a master's degree (41%), and a bachelor's degree (55%) in their educational history. In addition, 69% of the responders are between the ages of 15 and 25. When it comes to how often respondents visit and participate in river tourism, the majority (41%) say they do so at least once a year. 34% of respondents, however,

claim never to have engaged in river tourist activities.

The lack of a convenient river tourist site, fear of the river, and lack of time are the main excuses for non-participation. Many respondents affirmed that connecting with friends and family (45%) is the main reason for visiting rivers and taking part in river tourism activities. A separate group of participants enjoys leisurely river tourism (30%). Furthermore, a large number of participants stated that they combine enjoyment with visiting friends and family as a secondary goal of their river tourism excursions (VFR). Fewer respondents indicated that their trips were motivated by commercial or educational objectives.

Descriptive Analysis

In Table 2, the dependent variable 'Visitor Satisfaction with River Tourism' is shown together with the mean values and standard deviations of 14 attributes based on responses from surveyed visitors. The dependent variable's mean value is 3.26, which suggests that tourists who value river tourism services in Bangladesh are only moderately satisfied with the current range of options. As indicated by Table 2, a number of characteristics, including Scenic Beauty Richness, Hygiene and Cleanliness, Tour Management, Food Quality, and Cultural Attraction, play a major role in guaranteeing that visitors are satisfied with river tourism activities. Interestingly, with a mean score of 3.55, cleanliness and hygiene stand up as being very important in determining visitor happiness. Aspects include safety and security, variety of river-based activities, efficient crowd and noise control, comfort and convenience of boat services, and pricing methods should be the main focus in order to improve tourist satisfaction with river tourism overall. When taken as a whole, these elements help to provide a more positive experience for visitors taking part in river tourism around the nation.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Visitor Satisfaction	3.26	1.79	100
Quality of river tour	2.84	1.52	100
Safety and security	2.94	1.51	100
Cleanness	3.55	1.64	100
Comfort	1.94	1.05	100
Variety of activities	2.75	1.62	100
Environmental friendliness	2.65	1.70	100
Reasonable price	2.34	1.42	100
Organization and management	2.65	1.43	100
Friendliness	2.34	1.34	100
Scenery of river	3.29	1.75	100
Quality of food	2.85	1.49	100
Accessibility	3.1	1.64	100
Level of crowd	2.76	1.45	100
Cultural attraction	2.45	1.64	100
	3.044	1.61	100

Regression Analysis

The overall visitor satisfaction with river tourism is the dependent variable in this study, and the

impact of other factors on it was determined using multiple regression analysis. The factors related to "Safety and Security," "Cleanliness and Hygiene," and "Variety of River-based Activity," as shown in Table 3, all attained statistical significance at the 1% level. According to these results, visitor satisfaction in river tourism is positively impacted by a number of factors, including providing a variety of river-based activities, preserving cleanliness and hygiene, guaranteeing safety and security, charging a reasonable price, and managing service providers appropriately while travelling down rivers. The positive coefficient values suggest that these elements positively affect river tourism activities as well as tourist satisfaction. As a result, a rise in these factors is linked to an improvement in visitor satisfaction. It's crucial to remember that even while these particular factors have a direct impact on the dependent variable, this does not always mean that other independent variables have no influence.

Table 3. Regression Analysis

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.367	.392		.935	.353
	Guide skills	-.084	.092	-.071	-.915	.363
	Safety and security	.590	.101	.502	5.866	.000
	Cleanliness and hygiene of Boat	.320	.089	.293	3.589	.001
	Comfort and convenience of boat	.000	.128	.000	.003	.997
	Variety of activities on River Journey	.426	.081	.388	5.233	.000
	Environmental friendliness	-.090	.079	-.086	-1.137	.259
	Reasonable Price	.166	.094	.132	1.772	.080
	Management of tour	-.163	.092	-.131	-1.772	.080
	Friendliness and Professionalism of staff	-.138	.104	-.103	-1.326	.189
	Scenery of River	-.035	.075	-.034	-.459	.647
	Quality and Variety of Food	-.006	.100	-.005	-.061	.951
	Availability	-.046	.079	-.042	-.578	.564
	The level of crowd and noise Management	-.083	.093	-.067	-.889	.377
Cultural Attraction	.110	.082	.099	1.346	.182	

Exploratory Factor Analysis

By applying Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA), this study investigates the underlying correlations between measured variables to identify factors impacting visitor satisfaction in river tourism in Bangladesh. Descriptive statistics for specified characteristics are

generated before EFA is performed. The reliability of the measures is assessed using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sample adequacy and Bartlett's test of sphericity. A Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is used on 14 chosen parameters to determine the elements that contribute to tourist satisfaction in

Bangladeshi river tourism. PCA, a dimensionality reduction approach, compresses the attribute space from many variables to a smaller number of components in a non-dependent manner.

Table 3. Data Suitability and Sampling Adequacy

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.829
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	378.364
	df	91
	Sig.	.000

In order to ensure data compatibility for EFA, all variables are tested using the KMO and Bartlett's test. The KMO score of 0.829 exceeds the threshold of 0.60, suggesting superior sampling adequacy. The Bartlett's test produces a statistically significant result at the 0.00 level, indicating a strong link between variables and enabling for efficient PCA. Both KMO and Bartlett's Test confirm that the dataset is suitable for factor analysis. Principal Components Analysis using Varimax rotation of the 14 attributes yields four variables that account for 59.15 % of the total variation.

Practical Implication

River tourism in Bangladesh has grown in popularity due to the country's wide network of rivers and waterways. Despite this, tourist satisfaction is dependent on a variety of factors, which has significant implications for the management and growth of river tourism in Bangladesh. The report titled "Enhancing Visitor Satisfaction in Bangladeshi River Tourism: Identifying and Addressing Critical Factors" provides useful information for destination management and marketing. To begin, it emphasizes the importance of increasing safety and security measures, cleanliness, and accessibility in order to increase visitor pleasure. Second, the research

emphasizes the marketing of the destination's specific cultural and environmental characteristics in order to generate a memorable guest experience. Third, efficient management of visitor expectations is identified as a critical component determining satisfaction levels.

Furthermore, the findings argue for an overall improvement in the visitor experience to increase satisfaction, resulting in repeat visits and favorable word-of-mouth referrals (Wang et al., 2017). Destination marketers could focus on certain target niches, such as adventurers and nature enthusiasts. The study emphasizes the need of continuously monitoring visitor satisfaction levels in order to identify areas for development and shape future destination management and marketing initiatives. Infrastructure and facility quality are critical to visitor satisfaction. Hillary's 2020 study found that amenities like as bathrooms, lounging places, and food and beverage outlets had a substantial influence on visitor pleasure. As a result, establishing proper infrastructure is critical to improving the tourist experience. As M. Shahedul Alam et al. (2020) point out, safety and security play an important part in affecting tourist satisfaction in Bangladesh tourism. Providing safety precautions such as life jackets, first aid kits, and trained personnel is critical for instilling a sense of security and increasing happiness. Cleanliness and hygiene have an equal role in influencing tourist happiness, with impressions of the river and its environs having a considerable influence on overall contentment. Maintaining a clean atmosphere is critical to increasing guests' pleasure. Visitor happiness is directly related to service quality, namely the behavior and professionalism of tour operators and staff. Furthermore, the natural beauty and cultural attractions along the river greatly add to tourist delight. Promoting and sustaining these features can have a significant influence. To summarize, infrastructure, safety, cleanliness, service quality, and natural beauty all have an impact on tourist satisfaction in Bangladesh's river tourism industry. Addressing these characteristics has important practical consequences for the efficient development and administration of river tourism in the country.

Discussion

Further research on Enhancing Visitor Satisfaction in Bangladeshi River Tourism: Identifying and Addressing Critical Factors might focus on a number of crucial topics. One potential approach is to investigate the impact of cultural attractions and heritage preservation activities on tourist satisfaction. Given the importance of river tourism in exploring Bangladesh's cultural and natural legacy, knowing how preservation activities affect tourist pleasure is critical. Another important topic to study is the improvement of safety and security measures in river tourism, which may significantly improve the whole tourist experience. Furthermore, the use of creative marketing tactics and internet platforms to promote river tourism might improve tourist satisfaction. Furthermore, subsequent study might focus on enhancing tour management and putting emphasis on destination attractions. Diversifying river tourism activities to give tourists with more alternatives may also help to boost satisfaction. Given the critical role that local communities play in river tourism development and maintenance, researching their influence on tourist satisfaction might provide useful insights. Another topic worth investigating is the economic impact of river tourism on local communities and how this affects tourist pleasure. Furthermore, examining the impact of political stability on river tourism growth and tourist happiness is an important research topic. Examining service quality's role in the visitor experience, including the services provided by river tourism operators, can contribute to enhancing visitor satisfaction. It is also essential to understand the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on river tourism in Bangladesh and develop strategies to manage visitor expectations and concerns.

Conclusion

The study provides interesting information on the elements that influence visitor satisfaction with Bangladeshi river tourism. Visitors are relatively content with the service mix, as shown by the dependent variable's mean value, "Visitor

Satisfaction with River Tourism." Various attributes were discovered to influence visitor satisfaction with river tourism in Bangladesh. The study's findings indicate that the boat's cleanliness and sanitation, favourable management, river beauty, destination attractions, and degree of safety and security measures are all important predictors of tourist happiness. Furthermore, visitors' demographic factors, such as age, gender, and education level, were discovered to have a substantial influence on their happiness with the river tourism experience. To improve visitor satisfaction, players in Bangladesh's river tourism sector should focus on increasing management quality, destination accessibility, food quality, environmental friendliness, and tourist safety and security. Tour operators should be trained to improve their knowledge and abilities in the industry, and greater efforts should be made to meet the different demands and preferences of visitors. Overall, resolving these concerns will contribute to increased tourist satisfaction and the long-term development of Bangladesh's river tourism business. These findings might assist Bangladesh's river tourism operators and government improve tourist satisfaction and promote sector growth.

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Conflict of interests

There is no conflict of interest.

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